

From Data Center Inference to Edge Inference: A Latency Performance Evaluation

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Abstract: In recent years, the design trend of inference systems has shifted from data center–based inference to edge inference, and the demand for integrating both public cloud and edge resources is expected to grow rapidly. Significant architectural and operational differences exist between edge inference and traditional data center inference environments. Key design considerations include questions such as:

- Can the power supply be always on?
- Is an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) available?
- How much noise and heat are acceptable?
- How will the system be repaired, updated, or replaced?

Due to such physical and operational constraints, edge inference systems must operate with limited computational resources, stricter power budgets, and often within thermally restricted environments. Therefore, a high-speed and memory-efficient implementation is essential for achieving practical edge inference performance.

Keywords: Edge Inference

1. Introduction

Traditional inference system designs—optimized for stable, resource-rich data center environments—emphasized simplicity of the local execution context. In contrast, the current challenge lies in migrating inference workloads toward the edge, enabling broader scale-out and low-latency processing closer to the data source.

This technical note presents the key design considerations and performance evaluation results from transitioning data center inference to edge inference, using the NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier as the target edge device.

Certain aspects of traditional data center inference processing that rely heavily on abundant machine power and high-performance hardware subsystems cannot be directly replicated in edge environments. In particular, limitations in the instruction set architecture, CPU cache hierarchy, memory bus bandwidth, and internal data transfer mechanisms of edge devices impose significant design constraints.

The NVIDIA Jetson AGX Xavier, operating with a maximum power consumption of approximately 30 W, adopts a unified memory architecture shared between the CPU and GPU. This integration eliminates the need for explicit memory copies between processing units, reducing latency and improving throughput for workloads that combine heterogeneous compute resources.

When implementing real-time multimodal analysis—such as voice and image recognition—at the edge, system performance

Fig. 1: Traditional Design

can be further optimized through:

- efficient use of Unified Memory,
- pipeline design distributed across CPU cores,
- careful memory-access optimization,
- balanced CPU-core task allocation, and
- parallel execution of concurrent inference stages.

Together, these techniques enable high-performance inference under the strict power and thermal constraints inherent to edge computing platforms.

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Fig. 2: Edge Pipeline Design

In this study, we aim to design, implement, and evaluate an edge inference system capable of performing a complete real-time video processing pipeline, consisting of:

SDI input → inference → compositing → SDI/H.264 output.

The goal is to demonstrate that such a processing chain—traditionally executed in high-performance data center environments—can be effectively realized on a power-efficient edge platform, while maintaining low latency and real-time throughput.

2. Jetson AGX Xavier spec

Table 1: Jetson AGX Xavier 32GB Specification

Key	Value
AI Performance	32 TOPs (INT8)
GPU	512-core NVIDIA Volta™ GPU with 64 Tensor Cores
CPU	8-core NVIDIA Carmel Arm® v8.2 64-bit CPU 8MB L2 + 4MB L3
DL Accelerator	2x NVDLA
Vision Accelerator	2x 7-Way VLIW Vision Processor
Memory	32 GB 256-bit LPDDR4x 136.5 GB/s
Storage	32 GB eMMC 5.1
Power	10W / 15W / 30W
PCIe	1 x8 + 1 x4 + 1 x2 + 2 x1 (PCIe Gen4, Root Port & Endpoint)
CSI Camera	Up to 6 cameras (36 via virtual channels) 16 lanes MIPI CSI-2 8 lanes SLVS-EC D-PHY 1.2 (up to 40 Gbps) C-PHY 1.1 (up to 62 Gbps)
Video Encode	4x 4K60 8x 4K30 16x 1080p60 32x 1080p30 (H.265) 4x 4K60 8x 4K30 14x 1080p60 30x 1080p30 (H.264)
Video Decode	2x 8K30 6x 4K60 12x 4K30 26x 1080p60 52x 1080p30 (H.265) 4x 4K60 8x 4K30 16x 1080p60 32x 1080p30 (H.264)
Display	3 multi-mode DP 1.4 / eDP 1.4 / HDMI 2.0 No DSI support
Networking	10/100/1000 BASE-T Ethernet
Mechanical	100 mm × 87 mm 699-pin connector

Fig. 3: Unified Memory

Even within a resource-constrained edge inference environment, the combination of the Jetson Xavier’s Unified Memory architecture and a carefully designed software processing pipeline enables real-time video inference, as illustrated in Figure 4 below.

3. Audio Inference Pipeline and Preprocessing Bottlenecks

Conventional audio inference models typically follow a preprocessing chain of:

Audio PCM → Mel-spectrogram encoding → Image encoding → Image buffer generation.

This approach is computationally expensive and not well suited for real-time inference in resource-constrained edge environments. Each stage in the pipeline introduces latency due to sequential file I/O and redundant format conversions.

A typical process flow is as follows:

- Load Audio PCM data from the recording device.

Fig. 4: Predict Application

- Convert to a Mel-spectrogram representation.
- Encode the spectrogram as an image and output to local storage (LS).
- Read the image file back from local storage.
- Decode the image and convert it into a binary tensor buffer.
- Perform inference processing on the decoded data.

This multi-step data transformation pipeline, while convenient for offline training and visualization, is too slow and memory-intensive for real-time operation on edge devices. The overhead caused by repeated encoding/decoding and disk I/O dominates the total inference latency, making such architectures impractical for low-latency edge applications.

Fig. 5: Typical Block/Module

When deploying inference systems at the edge, it is necessary to account for irregular operating conditions, such as unexpected power loss, WAN communication failures, or other environmental instabilities. To accommodate these scenarios, we implemented a pass-through function that transmits inferred frames directly over the network in their H.264-encoded form, without additional

post-processing.

This mechanism proved particularly useful during the development and evaluation phases, as it allowed for quick visual verification of the inference state machine (FSM) and real-time inspection of inference results under unstable or recovery scenarios.

Fig. 6: Optimized Block/Module

4. Conclusion

In designing and implementing real-time audio and video inference at the edge, our evaluation confirmed that overall performance can be significantly improved by employing a per-CPU-core pipeline design in conjunction with the Unified Memory architecture of the Jetson Xavier. This configuration minimizes memory copy overhead and maximizes cache locality, thereby enabling stable real-time operation under constrained power and thermal conditions.

Additionally, through this work, we gained practical insights into the concurrent use of browser_fft from TensorFlow Lite Model Maker, which proved valuable for efficient frequency-domain feature extraction in audio inference tasks.